

Anodic Synthesis. Part I. Ester, Ether, Primary and Secondary Alcohols

J. K. Mehrotra and A. N. Dey

An ester, an ether, three primary, and three secondary alcohols have been prepared in fair yields by anodising appropriate mixtures of acids and half esters.

Kolbe (*Annalen*, 1849, **69**, 257) showed that on electrolysis of an aqueous solution of an alkali metal carboxylate, carbon dioxide and hydrocarbon were formed.

The electrolytic syntheses have, however, been largely restricted to the electrolysis of sodium salts of saturated carboxylic acids or half esters of α - β -dicarboxylic acids. The yields of the coupled products obtained depend to some extent on the structure of carboxylic acids employed and on experimental conditions (Swann, *Trans. Amer. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1929, **56**, 457; Fichter *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, **15**, 698; 1934, **17**, 1218; 1938, **21**, 141; Murray and Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1450).

The electrolysis of a mixture of carboxylic acids (R.COOH and R'.COOH) would give rise to products both by symmetrical and unsymmetrical (crossed) couplings (R.R, R'.R' and R.R'). The process is of wide application and affords a synthetical route to many organic compounds (Miller and Hofer, *Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 2427; Hofer, *Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 650; Carmichael, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **121**, 2545; Ruzicka *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, **15**, 1459; Kitaura, *Bull. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res., Japan*, 1937, **16**, 765; *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, **32**, 4523; Offe, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1947, **26**, 182; Gunstbee and Stenhagen, *Svensk Kem. Tidkr.*, 1942, **54**, 243; Hunsdiecker, *Ber.*, 1942, **75**, 447, 460, 1197; Weeden *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 3326, 3331, 3333). The advantage of the electrolytic process lies in the easy separability of the mixture of products in high purity. It has been found by earlier workers (Brown and Walker, *Annalen*, 1893, **42**, 274; Von Miller, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1897, **4**, 55) that even those acids which normally produce little or no yield of the Kolbe products, when electrolysed alone, afford cross-coupled products easily with other acids in fair yields. The relative proportions of the three products are those to be expected from the composition of the initial acid mixture. A wide difference in the size and structure of the two coupling units can be tolerated; this also includes cross coupling of simple and substituted fatty acids (I) with acid half esters (II) yielding hydrocarbons (III), mono-(IV), and dicarboxylates (V) (say Me):

With a view to standardising this method for the preparation of certain other compounds, an ester, an ether, three primary, and three secondary alcohols have been prepared by cross

Anodizing of mixtures of acids and half esters (Table I). As only cross-coupled products were required, in some cases the other products formed during electrolysis had not been fully worked up.

TABLE I

No.	Acids and half esters.	Cross-coupled products.	Yields (calc. from the acid).
1.	Butyric acid + ethyl hydrogen succinate	Ethyl caproate ^a	32% from butyric
2.	Phenylacetic acid + phenoxy-acetic acid	β -Phenoxyethylbenzene	13.7% from phenoxyacetic
3.	Lauric acid + glycollic acid	Lauryl alcohol	27.4% from lauric
4.	Myristic acid + glycollic acid	Myristyl alcohol	24.7% from myristic
5.	Palmitic acid + glycollic acid	Cetyl alcohol	13.7% from palmitic
6.	Lauric acid + lactic acid	<i>dl</i> -Tridecanol-2	20% from lauric
7.	Myristic acid + lactic acid	<i>d'</i> -Pentadecanol-2	22.4% from myristic
8.	Palmitic acid + lactic acid	<i>dl</i> -Heptadecanol-2	13.2% from lactic

EXPERIMENTAL

The apparatus used for electrolysis consisted of a boiling tube, 2" in diameter and 9" in length, fitted with a thermometer, a mechanically driven glass stirrer, a spiral anode of Pt wire, 24 swg and 20 cm long (total surface area 3.51 cm²), and a platinum plate cathode of 1.4 cm². The cell was clamped in a wide-mouth thermosflask, which was filled with a mixture of crushed ice and water so as to keep the cell cooled. The cell was connected in series with an ammeter, rheostat, and mains.

Ethyl Caproate.—Pure butyric acid (8.8 g., 0.1M) and ethyl hydrogensuccinate (14.6g., 0.1M) were dissolved in 50% methanol (100 c.c.). To this a solution of metallic sodium (0.46 g., 0.02 g. atom) in methanol (5 c.c.) was added. The mixture was placed in the anodising cell and a current of 2.2 amps. was passed through the cell for 3½ hours (theoretical current, 5.36 amps.) with vigorous stirring, while the cell was externally cooled by ice-water mixture to keep the internal temperature of the cell below 30°. At the end of the period the mixture became alkaline. The solvent was removed from the anodised solution at a low temperature. The distillate containing hexane^a (lit. b.p. 68.4°) was not further worked up. The residue was dissolved in ether (50 c.c.) and the ethereal layer was washed with small instalments of 2% NaOH solutions so as to remove last traces of any free acid. It was finally washed with two 10 c.c. portions of water. The organic layer was dried over fused CaCl₂. Ether was removed by distillation and the residue fractionally distilled. Two portions, one boiling below 190° and the other boiling between 190° and 250°, were collected. The latter on distillation gave 4.8 g. of pure diethyl adipate, b.p. 239-42° (lit. b.p. 245°). The former fraction on redistillation gave 4.6 g. of pure ethyl caproate^a, b.p. 167-68° (lit. b.p. 166-67°); caproic acid, b.p. 205° (lit. b.p. 205°); anilide, m.p. 95°.

β -Phenoxyethylbenzene.—A mixture of a solution of phenoxyacetic acid (15.2g., 0.1M), phenylacetic acid (13.6g., 0.1M), and sodium (0.46g., 0.02 g. atom) in 98% methanol (100 c.c.) was anodised by passing a current of 1.5 to 1.7 amps. for 5½ hrs., when the solution became alkaline. The solvent was removed from the anodised solution at a

low temperature and the residue dissolved in ether. The ethereal layer was washed with 1% NaOH and dried. The solvent was again removed and the residue distilled, collecting whole of the fraction passing between 90° and 180°/10 mm. The residue (7.8 g.) containing mainly diphenyl ethyl ether was not purified further. The distillate was refractionated, collecting 6.8 g. of dibenzyl, b.p. 137-41°/10 mm (lit. b.p. 140-50°/13 mm) and 2.7 g. of β -phenoxyethylbenzene, b.p. 168-70°/15 mm (lit. b.p. 162-63°/14 mm). (Found: C, 84.85; H, 6.38. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{14}O$: C, 84.85; H, 7.07%).

Lauryl Alcohol.—A mixture of a solution of lauric acid (20.0 g., 0.1M), glycollic acid (15.2 g., 0.2M), and sodium (0.69 g., 0.03 g. atom) in 98% methanol (100 c.c.) was anodised by passing a current of 1.5 to 1.7 amps. for 8 hours (theoretical time, 5.36 hours). The internal temperature was maintained below 30°. The anodised solution was frozen and filtered. The residue (A) was kept separately and from the methanolic filtrate the solvent was removed under diminished pressure; the residue was dissolved in ether, washed with 2% NaOH, and finally with water. The ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The ether was removed and the residue carefully distilled till the temperature reached 275°. While the distillate (B) was kept separately, the residue was mixed with (A). This on distillation gave 10.8 g. of pure docasaneⁿ, b.p. 220°/12 mm (lit. b.p. 224°/15 mm). The fraction (B) on refractionation gave 4.9 g. of ethylene glycol, b.p. 195-97° (lit. b.p. 197°) and 5.1 g. of lauryl alcohol, b.p. 150°/20 mm (lit. b.p. 255-59°). (Found: C, 77.42; H, 13.93. Calc. for $C_{12}H_{26}O$: C, 77.42; H, 13.98%). *p*-Bromobenzenesulphonyl, m.p. 49°; *p*-toluenesulphonyl, m.p. 30°.

Myristyl Alcohol.—A mixture of a solution of myristic acid (22.8 g., 0.1M), glycollic acid (15.2 g., 0.2M), and Na (0.69 g., 0.03 g. atom) in 98% methanol (150 c.c.) was anodised at 1.5 to 1.7 amps. for 8½ hours (theoretical time, 5.36 hrs). Internal temperature was kept between 30° and 35°. On working up the anodised solution as above, 8.3 g. of pure hexacosaneⁿ, m.p. 60° (lit. m.p. 59-60°), 5.0 g. of ethylene glycol, b.p. 91°/12 mm (lit. b.p. 197°), and 5.3 g. of myristyl alcohol, b.p. 160-65°/10 mm (lit. b.p. 160°/10 mm) were obtained. (Found: C, 78.11; H, 14.01. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{30}O$: C, 78.5; H, 14.02 %). *p*-Toluenesulphonyl, m.p. 35°; *p*-bromobenzenesulphonyl, m.p. 51.5°. Some amount of the final residue, containing impure hexacosaneⁿ, was also left. This was not further worked up.

Cetyl Alcohol.—A mixture of palmitic acid (25.6 g., 0.1M), glycollic acid (15.2 g., 0.2M), and Na (0.69 g., 0.03 g. atom) in 98% methanol (150 c.c.) was anodised at 1.5 to 1.7 amps. for 8 hours (theoretical time, 5.36 hrs.). The internal temperature of the cell was maintained between 40° and 50°. The anodised solution gave 14 g. of triacontane, m.p. 68° (lit. m.p. 68°), 5.7 g. of ethylene glycol, b.p. 91°/12 mm (lit. b.p. 197°), and 3.3 g. of cetyl alcohol, b.p. 178-83°/12 mm (lit. b.p. 190°/15 mm.). (Found: C, 79.7; H, 14.2. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{34}O$: C, 79.34; H, 14.05 %). *p*-Toluenesulphonyl, m.p. 37°; *p*-bromobenzenesulphonyl, m.p. 54°. The residue (4 g.), which had not been further worked, was left in the flask.

dl-Tridecanol-2.—A mixture of lauric acid (10. g., 0.05M), lactic acid (9 g., 0.1M) and Na (0.35 g., 0.015 g. atom) in 98% methanol (75 c.c.) was anodised at 1.5 to 1.7 amps. for 5½ hrs. (theoretical time, 2.68 hrs.). Internal temperature was maintained between 25° and 30°. The anodised solution gave 4 g. of docosaneⁿ, b.p. 218-20°/12 mm (lit. b.p. 224°/15 mm), 3.5 g. of butane-2,3-diol, b.p. 81-83°/12 mm (lit. b.p. 182.5°), and 2 g. of *dl*-tridecanol-2, b.p. 151-52°/12 mm (lit. b.p. 151°/11 mm). (Found: C, 77.61; H, 14.1. Calc. for $C_{13}H_{28}O$: C, 78.00; H, 14.0%). *Acid phthalate*, m.p. 58-59°.

dl-Pentadecanol-2.—A mixture of myristic acid (11.4 g., 0.05*M*), lactic acid (9 g., 0.1 *M*), and Na (0.35 g., 0.015 g. atom) in 98% methanol (100 c.c.) was anodised at 1.5 to 1.7 amps. for 6 hrs. (theoretical time, 2.68 hrs.). Internal temperature was maintained between 30° and 35°. The anodised solution gave 4.2 g. hexacosaneⁿ, m.p. 60° (lit. m.p. 59-60°), 3.4 g. of butane-2,3-diol, b.p. 81-83°/12 mm (lit. b.p. 182.5°), and 2.55 g. of *dl*-penta decanol-2, b.p. 163-65°/12 mm. (Found: C, 78.8; H, 13.71. C₁₅H₃₂O requires C, 78.95; H, 14.03%). Acid phthalate, m.p. 57.58°. The final residue (3.4 g.) was not further worked up.

dl-Heptadecanol-2.—A mixture of palmitic acid (12.9 g., 0.05*M*), lactic acid (9.0 g., 0.1*M*), and Na (0.35 g., 0.015 g. atom) in 98% methanol (100 c.c.) was anodised at 1.5 to 1.7 amps. for 6 hrs. (theoretical time, 2.68 hrs.). Internal temperature was maintained at 40-50°. The anodised solution yielded 6.8 g. of triacontane, m.p. 68° (lit. m.p. 68°), 3.5 g. of butane-2, 3-diol, b.p. 81-83°/12 mm (lit. b.p. 182.5°), and 2.3 g. of *dl*-heptadecanol-2, b.p. 185-87°/2 mm (lit. b.p. 140°/0.5 mm). (Found: C, 79.20; H, 13.81. Calc. for C₁₇H₃₆O: C, 79.69; H, 14.07 %). Acid phthalate, m.p. 63°. The final residue (2.4 g.) was not further worked up.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
D.A.V. COLLEGE, KANPUR.

Received June 7, 1961.

Anodic Synthesis. Part II. Homopilosinic Acid and *dl*-Homopilopic Acid

J. K. Mehrotra and A. N. Dey

Homopilosinic acid has been prepared by hydrolysis of the corresponding substituted butyric acid. In view of the difficulty in separating the mixture of isomeric acids obtained during the preparation of homologues¹ of this acid, a method, partly based on electrolysis, has been employed with success.

Isopilocarpine, on oxidation with KMnO₄ (Jowett, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 474, 851; 1901, 79, 581, 1331; Pinner, *ibid.*, 1903, 83, 438; Pinner *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1900, 33, 1424, 2357; 1901, 34, 727; 1902, 35, 204, 2443; 1905, 38, 2560), gives a mixture of pilopic acid (X: R=Et) and homopilopic acid (VII a: R=Et). Pilopic acid and isopilopic acid were synthesised by Tschitschibabin and Preobrashenski (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 460) from diethyl formylsuccinate. Preobrashenske *et al.* (*Ber.*, 1936, 69, 1835; *Bull. Acad. Sci., U. S. S. R.*, 1936, 993) converted *dl*-pilopic acid via pilopyl alcohol, chloride, and nitrile to *dl*-homopilopic acid. Preobrashenski *et al.* (*Doklady, Acad. Nauk. S. S. S. R.*, 1951, 81, 613), following the above procedure, have prepared several homologues of homopilopic acid.

Independently, Dey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1057) had prepared *dl*-homopilopic acid (VIIa: R=Et) and *dl*-homoisopilopic acid (VIIa: R=Et) by condensing ethyl γ -phenoxy-crotonate (I) with cyanoacetate and ethyl iodide and hydrolysing the substituted glutarate (II) formed.

Dey also prepared these acids by condensing ethyl 2-chloro-3-phenoxybutyrate (III), with ethyl malonate and ethyl iodide and hydrolysing the condensed product (IV):